

STUDYING THE ORGANIZATION OF ADVERTISING ACTIVITIES OF GOODS AT "SAMARKAND TEA PACKAGING FACTORY" JSC.

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

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Abstract. This article considers the development of ways to increase the use of advertising tools in the development of marketing activities in tea packaging JSC.

Keywords: tea, market, packaging, advertising, economy, consumption, commodity, exhibition.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ РЕКЛАМНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТОВАРОВ НА АО «САМАРКАНДСКАЯ ЧАЙНОУПАКОВОЧНАЯ ФАБРИКА».

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается разработка способов увеличения использования рекламных инструментов в развитии маркетинговой деятельности в чайной упаковке АО.

Ключевые слова: чай, рынок, упаковка, реклама, экономика, потребление, товар, выставка.

INTRODUCTION

According to the Ministry of Economy of Uzbekistan, in 2013, the volume of tea market in the country was 46.3 thousand tons. More than half (about 52%) of tea products are produced in China. In terms of the volume of tea supplied to Uzbekistan, Iran took the second place, and Sri Lanka took the third place. More than 142 different types and brands of tea are sold in the Republican food market today.

The rate of tea consumption in our republic is one of the highest in the world. However, today exactly 100 percent of the tea consumed in Uzbekistan is imported. Until the mid-90s of the last century, the main monopoly in the tea market of the republic was undoubtedly the Samarkand tea packing factory. About 20 enterprises are operating in the field of tea business and packaging in the republic. Nevertheless, Samarkand traditionally remains the tea capital of Uzbekistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

RESULTS

The purpose of our scientific research on the market of tea products is to propose ways to develop marketing activities of wholesale enterprises, including methods of promoting sales based on advertising means.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and performed in the article:

- to determine the essence of promotion of goods in modern business, its content and role in ensuring the effectiveness of marketing activities of enterprises.
- analysis of modern elements of promotion of goods in the industry, their characteristics and possibilities of use in different sectors of the economy;
- To study the development of the exhibition activity and advertising market at the current stage of development of market reforms in Uzbekistan;

- to study the features of advertising and exhibition activities in the tea business and the use of modern advertising tools;

- development of ways to increase the use of advertising tools in the marketing activities of the tea business.

Uzbekistan occupies one of the leading places in the world in terms of tea consumption - 2,650 grams per capita per year. For comparison, in Japan this indicator is only 680 grams, in the USA -430 grams, and in India even less - 290 grams. The main supplier of tea raw materials to our country is China (about 58% of the market). The second place in the volume of tea supply is Iran (25 percent), and the third place is Sri Lanka (4 percent). In addition, the commercial structures of Uzbekistan buy tea from the United Arab Emirates, Georgia, Turkmenistan and the Russian Federation. There are about thirty commercial structures in the republic, and tea production is a priority in their field of activity.

The Samarkand Tea Packing Factory was founded in 1840 by the Russian industrialist Fyodor Kuznetsov, who already had similar production facilities in Moscow, Odessa, Chelyabinsk and Vladivostok. According to information obtained from the Central State Archives of Uzbekistan, tea in bags was imported from China, India, Vietnam and even Argentina and packed by hand. In 1934, the factory was partially mechanized - equipment from the German company Nagema was installed on it.

Until 1920, there were 17 teahouses in Samarkand. In 1939, a tea packing factory was established on the basis of these suspensions. The construction of the production building began in 1935 and was completed in 1938.

In 1939, the first tea packing machine was adopted. The enterprise has 18 tea packing machines with a production capacity of 30,800 tons of packaged tea per year.

Resolution No. 15 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 12, 2005 "On measures for the development of the Samarkand tea packing factory". The factory was transformed into a foreign enterprise in the form of LLC (Limited Liability Company), the project capacity was 10-12 thousand tons of tea packaging per year, and it continuously strived for high quality and created its own brands. drinking tea paid off while maintaining democratic prices.

Today, after studying the market and the taste of consumers, the range of tea products is increasing year by year, and the quality of tea products is improving.

The annual capacity of the enterprise is 18,500 tons of packed tea.

26 tea packing machines were purchased from India, including 24 soft film packing machines, 2 carton packing machines, and 2 gram tea packing machines.

At the factory, tea is packed in bags of 40, 50, 80, 90, 100, 400, 1000, 2000 grams, as well as 2 grams and 8 kilograms.

For example, in 2015-2018, there were 50 named products, and by 2019-2021, there were more than 90 named products.

Quality control service: Here, experienced specialists, tea growers, and laboratory technicians check each batch of tea raw materials entering production. Only tea that meets the specified quality standards can be the basis for trademarks of the Samarkand Tea Packing Factory.

But that's not all: before leaving the factory, the products are packed in beautiful packaging and are again in the hands of quality service personnel. Finished product sampling

means that several packages from each new batch are opened, cooked and inspected. If experts have even the slightest doubt about the highest quality of tea, they wrap the whole batch, such a product will never enter the stores.

Tea production: But what do they do with the tea in the factory? First of all, it is cleaned with a complex multi-stage filtration system, which ensures that only selected tea leaves and no foreign matter are processed - and then on the table with you.

The tea is then stirred - or stirred. This is done to create tea with the optimal ratio of taste, aroma, strength and infusion color. In addition, the harvest in tea plantations varies throughout the year, and to prepare our favorite tea, we always have the same taste, each time we mix several, and sometimes up to ten - tea varieties from different plantations and harvested in different places. times of the year.

All these operations in the factory are fully mechanized. Machines precisely perform and automatically control each operation and the entire process. Thanks to modern equipment, the plant can quickly respond to changes in consumer demand, develop product types, and guarantee consumers excellent tea quality, first of all, its freshness.

The freshness of tea depends on two factors. First, the company has the opportunity to buy the best tea at the best price in the world market, which is a direct result of its scale of operation and excellent reputation. Secondly, the processing of tea in our enterprise and, first of all, its packaging is designed so that it does not lose even the slightest bit of its unique magic.

Price Advantage:

The favorable price is formed due to the scale of operations, efficient management of own production, the enterprise equipped with the most modern equipment, as well as a well-thought-out logistics system (for example: cheap import of unpackaged tea). rather than packaged tea, packaging is already done in Uzbekistan, the enterprise cooperates with suppliers at reasonable prices for raw materials.

Availability for consumers:

The most common throughout Uzbekistan;

Active brand support;

High consumer confidence in products.

At least every third tea buyer leaves the store with a product purchase, so many consumers prefer to buy tea from the company. The number of loyal customers is increasing year by year.

Table 1.

Dynamics of tea production and sales for 2020-2021

N	Indicator name	Unit	2020	2021 year	Departure from	in % until
o	Production	tn.	11,851.4	13 369.2	+1517.8	117.1
	Among them:					
	Green tea	tn.	10,596.6	11204.0	+607.4	113.1
	Black tea	tn.	1254.8	2165.2	+910.4	150.7

2	Implementation	tn.	10,866.6	13,258.0	+2391.4	127.7
	Among them:					
	Green tea	tn.	9 757.6	11,989.9	+2232.3	125.2
	Black tea	tn.	1 109.00	1268.1	+159.1	149.1

According to the data, in 2020, the company was able to sell 10,566.6 tons of tea, of which 1,109.0 tons of black tea, 9,575.6 tons of green tea, increased the assortment of tea products and updated the design of packaging materials. In 2021, the enterprise sold tea - 13873.3 tons, of which green tea - 12219.8 tons, black tea - 1653.5 tons.

Branch of "Samarkand Tea Packing Plant" JSCa plan of measures to attract consumers was developed, which made it possible to set forecast indicators for the volume of product sales for 2021 - 13,258.0 tons, that is, an increase of 127.7%, and product production increased by 117.1%. Figures 5 and 6 show the composition of tea sales in 2020 and 2021.

As we can see, the implementation of green tea in 2020 is 89.79%, and black tea is 10.21%. In 2021, green tea sales will be -88.08% and black tea sales will be 11.92%.

Indicators show that green tea accounts for the majority of consumption. Because green tea is a traditional drink in Uzbekistan.

Table 2.

Tea sales by month for 2020-2021.

2020				2021 year		
Month:	Total	Black tea	Green tea	Total	Black tea	Green tea
January	790.2	101.0	689.2	1062.2	139.8	922.4
February	827.3	94.9	732.9	1103.9	114.8	988.2
March	786.2	83.5	702.7	1177.1	146.1	1031.0
April	878.7	52.0	819.6	1140.6	146.8	993.8
May	1101.6	136.5	965.1	1124.6	147.9	976.7
june	979.9	39.7	940.3	1138.0	103.4	1034.6
july	932.0	97.6	834.4	1222.4	117.5	1104.9
August	989.6	59.3	930.3	1057.4	120.8	936.6
September	898.4	128.8	769.6	1136.9	114.2	1022.7
October	86.9	102.3	766.6	1213.6	140.1	1073.5
November	950.5	130.0	820.4	1325.7	182.3	1143.4
December	863.2	76.7	786.4	1170.8	179.6	991.2
Total:	10866.6	1109.0	9757.6	13873.3	1653.5	12219.8

According to Table 2, we can conclude about changes in the seasonality of tea consumption. The sales of tea at the Samarkand tea packing factory by month showed that the peak of sales in 2020 will be in May, and the minimum consumption in the winter months will be from November to March.

In 2021, the peak of tea sales will be in July, October and November, while the lowest sales will be in December and January.

Figure 7.

Composition of tea trade by month filiala IP "Samarkand Tea Packing Plant" in 2020.

According to estimates, the net income from product sales in 2021 amounted to -16,005.6 billion soums, an increase of 123.9% compared to 2020.

The reason is that the majority of the population of Uzbekistan consumes tea produced at the branch factory IP "Samarkand tea packing factory". Since the enterprise sells tea at the best prices, teas are delivered to all regions of the republic.

The organization of the marketing department in the enterprise is regulated by the regulation "On supply of finished products". The number of specialists consists of 3 people, headed by the head of the department.

Figure 8.

Composition of tea trade by month filiala IP "Samarkand Tea Packing Plant" in 2021.

A successful product sales strategy has a positive effect on the financial performance of "Samarkand Tea Packaging Factory" (Table 3).

Table 3

Average financial indicators of tea "Samarkand Tea Packing Plant" JSC branch

o	Indicator name	Unit rev.	2020	2021 year	Departure from 2020	in % until 2020
ne	Net proceeds from the sale of finished goods	billion soum	105281.2	130416	+25134.8	123.9
	Net profit	billion soum	9924.4	15400	+5475.6	155.2

DISCUSSION

The main activities of the department are as follows:

- preparation and analysis of the market for a comfortable perception of products - marketing research;
- to support the demand at the stage of mass production of goods at a high level - to issue colorful catalogs of finished products, to provide advertising of finished products;
- to help expand the sales market - to participate in exhibitions and fairs.

The following are given in the organization of marketing activities of the enterprise:

- opportunities and threats;
- strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise;
- rating criteria for choosing one or another type of tea depending on age;
- the effect of age on the choice of tea varieties;
- reasons for eating and not eating different types of tea.

An example of demand support at the stage of mass production is the use of color advertising on television, social networks, the Internet and other publications.

Below are some elements of online advertising targeting the taste of certain types of products.

Jasmine green tea perfectly refreshes, invigorates, refreshes. The aroma of jasmine penetrates deeply, helps to open and improve the permeability of all energy channels of the body. This is manifested in the appearance of a feeling of freshness, in an uplift of mood. Jasmine also has a positive effect on vision.

Long-leaf green tea, unlike black tea, is made from tea leaves that are steamed for 1.5-2 minutes to destroy enzymes. The sheet is then dried, rolled, sorted and dried to a standard moisture content. Ready tea contains chlorophyll, vitamin C, tannins and other biologically active substances, tea has a clear healing and thirst-quenching effect. Green tea is divided into leaf and small.

CONCLUSIONS

Today, black tea with bergamot is more popular and popular. It is not only a delicious drink that is suitable for any table. This tea can be called a health and even healing drink. Regular consumption of this tea will significantly improve your appearance. The skin gets rid of acne, freckles, becomes light, smooth and healthy both in appearance and in reality. In addition, bergamot tea is useful for relieving fatigue accumulated in the middle of the working day and successfully ending the day. This tea relaxes, but at the same time gives strength.

We offer black tea packaged. The taste of black tea is devoid of bitterness, the infusion has an orange or red color. Tea has both a tonic and soothing complex effect. Quality products at affordable prices.

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